

Correct formation of practical classes in design education.

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Abstract: In the article, the author determines the essence of the factors that each of the training sessions has its own methodological example of the creative activity of students and serves as a catalyst for the experimental work of artists.

Keywords: experimental, innovative education, method, development.

Currently, there are several points of view on defining the essence of the concept of “design”. The Dictionary of Foreign Words defines design as: a) the artistic design of objects; b) designing the aesthetic appearance of industrial products. N. M. Shansky explains the word “design” in the etymological dictionary of the Russian language. The English word “design” means in one case “to conceive, design, construct”, in another – “plan, project, construction, drawing”.

The profession of a designer requires specialists to have artistic imagination, creativity, and spatial thinking. Today, it seems extremely important to form and develop design thinking, since without it it is impossible to imagine the activities of a designer.

A designer student prepares for the following activities:

- development of artistic and design (design) projects for industrial products, object-spatial complexes;
- technical execution of artistic and construction (design) projects in the material;
- control over the manufacture of products in production in terms of compliance with their original design;
- organizing the work of a team of performers;
- performance of work in one or more professions of workers, positions of employees – performer of artistic and design works.

All this cannot be accomplished without developed design thinking, which presupposes the presence of a certain amount of special knowledge (design, artistic, etc.).

Focusing on the expert opinion of teachers, we have identified some signs of underdeveloped design thinking among students in this specialty:

- lack of independence, inability to think without relying on traditions, examples (breaking traditions, a certain disobedience to rules is encouraged in design);
- lack of dialogue, openness (unlike the thing being created, which must be a finished form, the thought process, on the contrary, must be incomplete, open to dialogue with the consumer, aimed at improving the project);
- lack of conceptuality (breaking the old, you need to imagine the new, what will take shape in the vacant space).

The designer is obliged to put forward a concept, a general idea, otherwise his original ideas will most likely have a tinge of posing).

To be successful as a designer, it is necessary to develop design thinking. Designers' thinking occurs in the process of creative activity. Active learning methods are increasingly recognized, such as:

- discussion methods (free and directed discussions, meetings of specialists, discussion of life and professional incidents, etc.);
- gaming methods (business, organizational and activity-based, simulation, role-playing games, psychodrama, social drama, etc.);
- rating methods (efficiency ratings, popularity ratings);
- training methods (behavioral and personality-oriented trainings).

One of the most effective methods of active learning is a business game. Verbitsky A. A, Platov V. Ya, Khrutsky E. A, Borisova N. V, Selevko G. K, and others were involved in the development and use of business games for students.

In the works of Abramova G.S., Stepanovich V.A, the idea is considered that a business game is both a form and a method of teaching, in which the subject and social aspects of the content of professional activity are modeled. Thus, a business game will help not only to develop students' design thinking, but also to intensify

their activities in the classroom, develop communication skills, and also introduce them to professional activities.

Variability and flexibility of thinking allow you to create and develop not one, but several project options that meet the goal. A creatively thinking designer tries to build as many hypotheses as possible, from which one can choose the best option, or one can develop many options as varieties of a creative solution to a problem. The variability of thinking, of course, increases with the expansion of experience and knowledge, but in addition to them, the use of appropriate methods that specifically stimulate the solution of creative problems also plays an important role in the educational process.

A sense of style and stylistic harmony allows one to approach the assessment and creation of the surrounding subject environment as a single whole. The concept of “style” means precisely stable unity. Usually this unity is expressed through certain signs and techniques of artistic design, about which students must also have the appropriate knowledge. Thus, today it seems extremely important to form design thinking, without which it is impossible to imagine design activity.

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